

v1 Examining the Lombard Effect in Non-native Speakers

This DMP was created in RIS for Students

General information

1.1 Title of this DMP

Examining Lombard Speech in Non-native Speakers

1.2 Summary of the research proposal

In my research, I study Lombard speech, how people speak when there is noise. Lombard speech is different from speech produced in quiet environments (plain speech) in terms of acoustics (e.g., fundamental frequency (pitch), intensity (loudness), duration of words, and energy). As Lombard speech has greatly been studied in native speakers, I have decided to study non-native speakers to see if non-native speakers' Lombard speech is the same as native speakers.

For this purpose, I will record 10 native Dutch speakers and 10 native English speakers reading English sentences in a quiet environment and then reading sentences while listening to noise, producing (native and non-native English) plain and Lombard speech. The Dutch native speakers will come back for a second session to record Dutch sentences in quiet and in noise producing native Dutch plain and Lombard speech.

I will extract several acoustic measures from the recorded speech and analyze this. I will compare the acoustics of non-native English Lombard speech to native English Lombard speech and see if they are the same. If there are differences then comparing the non-native English Lombard speech to the native Dutch Lombard speech will reveal if the non-native speech is influenced by the native language or whether it is different because of the extra effort of speaking a non-native language.

1.3 At which research institute and/or as part of which BA/MA programme and course is the research project conducted?

This DMP is written for a research project which is part of the thesis course for the Research Master's Linguistics and Communication Sciences.

1.4 If applicable: What are the project number, funder and funder ID?

I am part of a larger project under John Smith and the project number is 0000000000.

1.5 What is the (expected) start and end date of the project?

September 2023 - June 2024

1.6 Who is your supervisor for this project?

John Smith
Henrietta Jackson

1.7 Which researcher(s) and/or relevant parties are involved in the research project, and what are their roles regarding data management?

Involved in writing and adjusting the DMP:
Katherine Marcoux

Involved in data collection and analysis:
Katherine Marcoux
Henrietta Jackson

Involved in data storage during research:
Katherine Marcoux
Henrietta Jackson

Involved in long-term data archiving and sharing after the project, including transfer of data management roles:
John Smith
Henrietta Jackson

1.8 Who is the rightsholder of the data that you will collect and/or generate during the project?

The rightsholder of the research data is Radboud University.

1.9 Did you consult a supervisor or an RDM expert when writing this DMP? If yes, specify who you consulted.

Yes, I consulted Henrietta Jackson for feedback

Data collection

- 2.1 Will existing data be (re-)used for this research project? If yes, please specify the data, their source and the terms of re-use.
No, no existing data will be (re-)used during the project.
- 2.2 Will new data be generated within the research project? If yes, please specify the collection process and the data that will be generated, including file formats.
Yes, new data will be generated during the project. The collection process and the data that will be generated are as follows:
I will record 10 native Dutch and 10 native English speakers reading English sentences I created in a quiet environment and when listening to noise. The native Dutch speakers will additionally read sentences in Dutch in quiet and in noise. The recordings will be in .wav format. I will extract acoustic measures and save them in a .txt file. The analyses will be conducted in R, for which there will be a .R file.

Personal data

- 3.1 Do any of the project's data allow identification of a person? In other words, are you working with personal data? List all types of data in your dataset which could be used for identification.

Do not forget about

- data that you use for participant recruitment, contact information, the key file of pseudonymised data, etc.
- data that can lead to identification when combined (e.g. place of residence and job description in some cases)
- personal data that you do not specifically ask for, but participants may provide in response to an open question in a questionnaire or during an interview

- Names
Participants will fill out their names in the informed consent forms.
- Audio recordings of participants
I will be recording participants
- SONA ID or other ID in a participant recruitment system, namely:
I will recruit participants via SONA

- 3.2 Do your data contain special categories of personal data? List all categories and specify the data.

Be aware that special categories of personal data are subject to strict legal conditions.

- No, my data do not contain special categories of personal data

- 3.3 Will you anonymise or pseudonymise the data in order to protect the privacy of your participants? If yes, how?

No, my data cannot be anonymised/pseudonymised, because:
I have audio data which cannot be anonymised/pseudonymised.

- 3.4 Do you need approval from an ethics committee for your project? Please explain why (not).

Yes, I need approval from an ethics committee for my project, because:
I am working with human participants.

- 3.5 Do you need to use an informed consent procedure?

Yes, I work with human participant data and will use the following informed consent procedure:
The informed consent procedure established by the Ethics Assessment Committee Humanities at Radboud University, as specified [here](#).

Storing and sharing during research

4.1 Explain where you will store your data during research.

Name *all* storage facilities and/or devices you will use during research, even when only used temporarily.

- Radboud University workgroup folder
I will store and work on (parts of) my data in a Radboud University workgroup folder (i.e., “werkgroepmap”) on the university’s network drive. My supervisor can request a folder for me. The data are automatically backed up on a regular basis. When off-campus, I can securely access the data through a VPN connection.

When I do not have a (stable) internet connection, I will work on an encrypted computer or - if necessary - on an encrypted USB stick. I will transfer the data to my workgroup folder as soon as possible.

- I will make use of a different kind of safe storage, namely:
When recording the audio files, the data will be stored temporarily on the recording device's SD card. This data will be moved to the Radboud University workgroup folder as soon as possible and deleted from the SD card.

4.2 How will you share your data during research and with whom? Specify whether they are Radboud researchers or from a different Dutch or international institute.

Be aware that sharing personal data should be kept to a minimum. Furthermore, not all tools are suitable for sharing personal data, see the 'i'-button for details on the options below.

- Radboud University workgroup folder
I will use a workgroup folder to share data with my supervisor.

Long term archiving and reuse

5.1 Where will you archive your data (including raw data, metadata, and documentation) for at least 7 years for the sake of scientific integrity?

This may be done in an internal or public archive. Be aware that personal data that are not necessary for answering the research question (e.g. contact details of participants) must be deleted as soon as possible and should not be archived, regardless of the choice of archive.

I will use the data archiving option in RIS for students to archive my data for a minimum of seven years.

5.2 Will you make (parts of) your research data publicly available for re-use and replication purposes? Please specify where and when and whether any restrictions or embargoes apply. If you are not making your data publicly available, provide a valid reason for not sharing your data.

Be aware that you are not allowed to share personal data publicly unless you have explicit permission from your participants through informed consent.

No, I will not make my research data publicly available, because:

The audio data is personal data and I did not ask my participants if I could make their audio recordings public.